

COOPERATION OF PARENTS AND CLASS LEADERS IN THE EDUCATION OF STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

In the family, the role of teachers and parents is very large in bringing up students mature and perfect. The article discusses the cooperation of the class leader and parents, the class leader's ability to manage the class team.

Parents have great hearts. The person who enriches this soul is the teacher. Parents should support teachers when it comes to education, but we blame teachers for any problems that arise with students. But if we compare the duties of the teacher with the parents, it becomes clear which responsibility is better. In fact, the real teacher of the student is his parents. The way parents look at school, the child looks at it the same way. Therefore, the teacher's success in developing children's abilities mainly depends on the example of parents in the family. In other words, parents should support school teachers in teaching and educating children:

First: You should not take the child's side when he does something wrong.

There is no person in this world who does not make mistakes. Especially children make a lot of mistakes. The essence of education is to realize your mistakes after you have made them. Therefore, if a child is late for school, does not do homework, or misbehaves in class, it is the biggest mistake parents ever make.

Instead, explain why he did something wrong. Parents should explain children's misbehavior rather than teachers. Because a teacher can educate a child, but when it comes to education, the influence of parents is much greater than that of the teacher. The child should know that when he does something wrong, he will be punished, and he may even become very timid. He will eventually get used to it, if not quickly. Thus, the parents themselves witness the gradual improvement of their child's education.

Second: Don't belittle the child, find out if he does what is said!

If you ask your kids what they want to eat every night, they'll all say ice cream without a doubt. There is nothing surprising here, because they do not need to be able to distinguish the

abundance or usefulness of what they eat. The same goes for homework. Homework can seem like a big problem to a child. Children take care of everything and try to get rid of them as soon as possible. He glances at his homework and tells me to go to the computer or the TV as soon as possible. It is clear from this that how can we make sure that our child can do homework completely and without mistakes?

There is only one answer to this question that life has left before us: the correct performance of parental duty is in the general sense. It is the duty of parents to fully control whether the child eats properly or not. Similarly, it is the responsibility of parents to know what assignments are given at school and to monitor their completion. If a child knows that his parents supervise his schoolwork, he will also develop a sense of responsibility. So know if your child is doing their homework and never neglect them!

Third: Be careful of things that prevent the child's talent from unfolding!

Computer games, in a word, are a child's greatest enemy.

Devices such as televisions and mobile phones prevent the child from socializing, taking away physical exercise in the fresh air and, most importantly, reading.

If parents can keep children away from these devices as much as possible, they will be doing teachers a huge favor.

This should not be understood as a "complete ban on the use of technology". But it is necessary to keep a certain limit.

For example, it is better not to watch TV more than one hour a day.

It is better to play computer games on weekends or when there are no classes.

Cell phones are also one of the hot issues of today. It is not right not to have mind-boggling games on the phone, as well as to sleep on the phone day and night.

Instead of playing computer games, encourage children to read books and participate in community activities. Only then can you save them from the confusion of technology!

Fourth: Be an example to them!

As mentioned above, a child first takes an example from his parents. In other words, what you are, your child will be like you.

If you don't have a book in hand, if you don't check your child's homework and if you eat in front of the TV every day, your child will repeat what you did.

But if you read a book for a while before going to bed, if you are interested in your child's lessons and turn off the TV after dark, the child will get used to it. Children of wise parents will also be wise. If you want your child to be like you, first follow it yourself and set an example for him!

Fifth: Always communicate with teachers, don't block their way!

Support teachers! After all, isn't it said that a person who chooses such a profession is not to get rich as a "teacher", but to educate the young generation?! If so, it is necessary for parents to support teachers in every way.

"You put a low rating"! It is not right to tempt the teacher! By assigning a low grade to the student, the teacher attracts the attention of the parents and tells them that they need to help

their child prepare for classes. Parents should try to understand the teacher correctly. In short, the teacher does not wish harm to any parent. Because he loves every student as his own child.

Teachers who have just started their careers, especially, should look with hope at the future of each student, try to approach it individually, do not use methods of educational punishment in a disorderly manner, and strive to set promising educational goals for the group of students.

The main tasks of learning the teacher's etiquette course are as follows:

- to provide future teachers with knowledge, qualifications and skills related to universal and national ethics, professional ethics, teacher etiquette;
- manage, direct, organize and control the interaction and relations between the teacher and students, colleagues, parents, school leaders during the educational process;
- defining the moral standards that must be followed by the behavior and moral relations between the participants of the pedagogical process, inculcating the need to follow them into the minds of future pedagogues;
- teaching students and future teachers ways of moral self-education;
- to increase the spiritual and moral level of future teachers, pedagogical and moral culture.

If young teachers do not strive to master the secrets of certain pedagogical skills, if their knowledge of their subject is shallow, if they do not approach interpersonal relations creatively, if they do not improve their communication skills, then students will gradually stop recognizing them. As a result, irreparable errors may appear in the communication between the teacher and students.

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